
ORGANIZING THE USE OF DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES BY STUDENTS IN THE CONDITIONS OF DISTANCE EDUCATION

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Abstract.

This article provides information about the concept of digital educational technologies and their use in the educational process in the conditions of distance education in higher education institutions.

Key words.

distance education, educational technologies, online course, webinar, e-learning environment, digital education, online.

Аннотация.

В данной статье представлена информация о понятии цифровых образовательных технологий и их использовании в образовательном процессе в условиях дистанционного обучения в высших учебных заведениях.

Ключевые слова.

дистанционное образование, образовательные технологии, онлайн-курс, вебинар, электронная образовательная среда, цифровое образование, онлайн.

In universities of foreign countries, great attention is paid to the use of teaching technologies through distance education and the creation of an electronic learning environment.

Today, teaching in the electronic educational environment consists of improving the educational process based on the principles of automating education, designing and using methods and materials that serve to increase the effectiveness of education.

According to V.I.Slobodchikov's scientific research, if there is an educational environment, its content, connections, and tools will exist.

D. N. Mamatov, one of the scientists of the Republic of Uzbekistan, defined the concept of the electronic-informational educational environment as a set of software, information technology, educational methodical systems that provide a specific goal-oriented educational process.

E-learning environment is a synonym of informational learning environment, based on modern information technologies in order to meet the needs of users for educational resources. reefered.

T.G.Vezirov, A.M.Patkhon emphasize that the e-learning environment opens new horizons for the teacher, and this environment requires the teacher of the higher education system to use information and communication technologies at a high level. This is one of the necessary conditions for the teacher of information and communication technologies to continuously improve his skills and professional training to work in the information education environment.

D.N. Mamatov described the electronic-informational educational environment according to the following typological signs:

1. The electronic-informational educational environment at any level is considered to be an object with a complex structure of a systemic nature.

2. The integrity of the electronic-informational educational environment is synonymous with the concept of achieving systematicity, meaning their harmony, and embodies the goals of education and training in the implementation of the model of the graduate of the educational institution.

The electronic-informational educational environment is a factor affecting the effectiveness of education and training, as well as its tool.

A.A.Abduqadirov has conducted scientific research on issues such as the use of information technologies to increase the efficiency of students' learning in the teaching of computer science, the use of modern information and pedagogical technologies in the educational process, the introduction of distance education into practice, the advantages and disadvantages of distance education.

The goal of creating an electronic learning environment is not only to acquire the necessary knowledge, skills and abilities in an information society, but also to significantly increase students' mental activity, interest in educational activities, their attitude to the process of acquiring new knowledge, and the emotional mood of education. B.M. Suropov applied this suggestion in his scientific researches to work on e-learning.

A.A.Andreev, E.Simonlar showed in their studies that "the informational educational environment is a pedagogical system and its supply unit, a subsystem of financial, economic, material, technical, regulatory and marketing management."

Nevertheless, scientists have taken different approaches to the study of e-learning environments. Digital technologies, dynamic and static systems, system

requirements, planning and creation stages used in the creation of Sh.B. Bekchanova e-learning platform are covered.

In his works, N.A. Muslimov conducted a comparative analysis of the organization of the educational system on the basis of information technologies, the use of active learning methods, provision of educational and methodological complexes, and the organization of distance education.

R. Sharpe studied the use of e-learning in many higher education institutions, while Rosenberg and Snart showed the use of popular open online and distance courses in education. Mayes and De Freitas consider it a cost-effective method and means of achieving learning outcomes and student knowledge assessment in distance education.

U.Yu.Yuldashev conducted scientific research on the use of information technologies in the educational system, creation of a single information space, resource and hybrid, intellectual inter-system relations, expert training systems.

Electronic management systems for distance learning around the world:

Digital Learning Management Systems:

Blackboard - resources and tools for quality online teaching and learning;
CenturyTech-one-on-one micro-lessons to bridge knowledge gaps, exercise, and improve long-term memory.

ClassDojo is an app that connects teachers, students, and parents to create community classrooms.

Edmodo - Tools and resources for classroom management and remote student engagement.

Edraak - Online Arabic learning with resources for students and teachers;

EkStep is an open learning platform with a collection of learning resources to support literacy and numeracy learning;

Google Classroom - helps classes connect, communicate and organize learning remotely.

Moodle is a community-driven open learning platform with worldwide support;

Nafham is an online Arabic language learning platform that includes video lessons tailored to the Egyptian and Syrian curriculum;

Schoology - tools to support teaching, learning, alignment, collaboration and assessment;

View Cart is an application that enables the creation of collaborative and shared digital learning materials and resources;

Skooler - tools for turning Microsoft Office software into a learning platform;

Studuri Sapuri is an online Japanese language learning platform for school students.

Systems specially developed for mobile phones:

Cell-Ed is a student-centered, skills-based learning platform with offline options;

Eneza Education - editorial and educational materials for basic feature phones;

Funzi is a mobile learning service that supports teaching and learning for large groups;

KaiOS is software that brings smartphone capabilities to affordable mobile phones and helps open portals to learning opportunities;

Ubongo is an app that uses entertainment, media and mobile to provide localized education at an affordable cost and scale to African families;

Ustad Mobile - offline access and sharing of educational content.

Systems with advanced offline functionality:

Can't wait to learn - game technology that provides quality education for children, including in conflict situations;

Kolibri is a curriculum to support universal education;

Rumie - lifelong learning tools and materials for underserved communities;

Ustad Mobile - offline access and sharing of study materials.

Massive open online course (MOOC) platforms:

Alison - expert online courses;

Coursera is an online course taught by instructors from renowned universities and companies.

EdX - online courses of leading educational institutions;

People's University is an online university open to higher education;

Icourses - Chinese language courses for university students;

Future Learn - Online courses for students to learn, develop professional skills and connect with professionals.

Canvas is continuous learning and professional development for teachers.

Educational materials for independent work:

Byju's - Curriculum with large repositories of learning materials suitable for different grades and learning levels;

Discovery Education - Free educational resources and lessons on various levels of viruses and epidemics;

Geekie is a Portuguese-language web platform that provides personalized educational content using personalized learning technology.

Khan Academy - Free online courses, lessons and practical assignments;

KitKit School is a tablet learning kit with a comprehensive curriculum for young children and beginners;

LabXchange is user-generated and user-driven digital educational content delivered on an online platform that provides a learner and research experience;

Mindspark is a flexible online learning system that helps students practice and learn math;

Mosoteach is a Chinese-language application for hosting classes in the cloud;

OneCourse is a child-friendly curriculum for reading, writing and counting;

Quizlet - learning through flashcards and games to support learning in multiple subjects.

Siyavula - Mathematics and Physics education according to the South African curriculum;

YouTube is a huge repository of educational videos and educational channels.

Apps for mobile reading:

African Storybook - Open access collection of stories in African languages;

Global digital library - digital reading materials can be easily accessed from mobile phones or computers;

StoryWeaver is a digital repository of multilingual stories for children;

Worldreader - digital books and stories that can be used on mobile devices and features to support reading habits;

Dingtalk is a communication platform that supports video conferencing, task and calendar management, visit tracking, and instant messaging;

Lark is a suite of collaboration tools that includes chat, calendaring, content creation, and cloud storage.

Hangouts Meet is video calling integrated with other Google G -Suite tools.

Skype - video and audio calls with chat, messaging and collaboration functions;

Zoom is a cloud platform for video and audio conferencing, collaboration, chats and webinars.

Digital Learning Content Creation Tools for Teachers:

Thinglink - tools for creating interactive images, videos and other multimedia resources;

Buncee - multimedia lessons, reports, newsletters and presentations;

EdPuzzle is a video tutorial creation program;

Kaltura - Video management and creation tools with integration capabilities for various learning management systems;

Nearpod is software for creating lessons with informative and interactive assessment activities;

Pear Deck - facilitates the development of educational content with various integration features;

Squigl is a content creation platform that converts speech or text into animated video.

Foreign universities are at the top in the field of training of informatics specialists in distance education in higher education institutions. Its development is particularly important in all countries, especially in the USA, England, Switzerland, Norway, Canada, France, China, Korea, and Russia.

As a result of the use of modern methods in the conditions of distance education, students are able to think independently, analyze, draw the necessary conclusions, express their opinion freely, defend it based on the basis, conduct active communication, discussion, debate. skills develop. These methods serve to increase the activity between tutors and students in distance education, to activate the learning of students, to develop their personal qualities, and to increase the effectiveness of training by using interactive methods.

At present, the widespread use of such technologies in many large foreign educational institutions is a proof of our opinion. The widespread use of such modern high technologies in education by representatives of various educational disciplines is considered an important principle in increasing the effectiveness of education and its intensification, and facilitates the organizational and methodical support of the future informatics teacher training system.

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